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Enhancing public service delivery efficiency: Exploring the impact of AI

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) adoption on public service delivery efficiency in India. It addresses a significant gap in existing literature by investigating the impact of AI adoption on public service delivery efficiency in India, a context that has not been extensively explored. Through a comparative analysis approach, the study assesses the effectiveness of AI applications in enhancing public service delivery. The quantitative research design employed in the study draws on previous literature on AI integration in governance and focuses on Chief Information Officers (CIOs) as primary respondents. The findings reveal significant improvements in citizen-centric services and municipal processes due to AI adoption. However, the impact on human-centric aspects is found to be moderate. The study also underscores the importance of infrastructure readiness for successful AI implementation. Notably, only 25% of organizations were found to be possessing advanced technological infrastructure. This research is original in its focus on Chief Information Officers (CIOs) as primary respondents and its comparative analysis approach to assess the effectiveness of AI applications in enhancing public service delivery. This study offers valuable insights for policymakers and practitioners. Emphasizing the need for effective policies and infrastructure development, it highlights the potential of AI to eliminate corruption risks and enhance overall efficiency and transparency in public service delivery mechanisms.

1. Introduction

In an era of rapid technological advancement, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into various sectors has become inescapable. One such application is in public service delivery, where efficiency and effectiveness are crucial for ensuring good governance by the government and citizen satisfaction. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) notes that governance covers every facet of a country's administration, incorporating its economic strategies, regulatory structure, and commitment to upholding the rule of law. Effective governance entails ensuring justice, empowerment, employment, transparency, and the proficient delivery of services to all citizens (Singh, 2008; Kalsi et al., 2009). Conventional methods of governance are often hindered by bureaucratic red tape and resource constraints, resulting in inefficiencies in service delivery (Gupta, 2023). Efficient governance requires timely and accurate delivery of services to meet the diverse needs of the citizens while optimizing resource utilization and minimizing

bureaucratic hurdles. The advent of AI has opened up huge opportunities to revolutionize governance practices and enhance service delivery efficiency.

With a huge potential for data analysis, pattern recognition, and automation, AI presents a promising solution to many of the challenges faced by conventional governance systems. By harnessing AI technologies, governments can streamline processes, improve decision-making, and enhance service delivery to the citizens. Leveraging the advancements in technology, India too is harnessing the capabilities of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to redefine its governance and public services, heralding a new era of citizen-centric administration (ZeeBiz, 2023).

As one of the fastest-growing economies in the world, India has a substantial stake in the AI revolution. The National Strategy for AI proposed by the NITI Aayog - National Institution for Transforming India, the apex public policy think tank of the Government of India - has noted that numerous countries across the globe have established specialized public offices, such as the Ministry of AI in the UAE and the

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Office of AI and AI Council in the U.K. Meanwhile, China and Japan have empowered existing ministries to spearhead AI implementation within their respective sectoral domains. The National governments of countries like China, the USA, France, and Japan have substantially augmented public funding for AI by making commitments such as raising expenditures on research and development, establishing industrial and investment funds for AI startups, investing in network and infrastructure, and engaging in AI-related public procurements (NITI Aayog, 2018). The Union Government of India in its budget 2023–24 has also outlined plans to establish three AI centers of excellence within the premier educational institutions in the country, marking a noteworthy stride towards the realization of “AI in India” and “AI for India” (Inc42, 2023).

In the era of globalisation, India’s ability to leverage AI for governance can enhance its competitiveness on the global stage. By embracing AI-driven innovations in governance, India can position itself as a leader in leveraging technology for the public good, setting an example for other nations facing similar governance challenges. In this regard, the Government of India’s vision of ‘Minimum Government, Maximum Governance’ also aims at establishing a system where administration and good governance operate smoothly without unnecessary interference or hurdles. Thus, harnessing Top of Form

harhah AI in governance and public policy presents a significant opportunity for citizen engagement, accountability, interoperability, and successful delivery of public services. It also provides governments with a chance to enhance efficiency in their administrative processes (Confederation of Indian Industry, 2023). Top of Form

The primary objective of this study is to investigate and comprehend the impact of AI implementation on public service delivery efficiency in India. Firstly, the study aims to examine the maturity level of AI adoption in municipal corporations in India specifically focussing on dimensions such as awareness and understanding, current AI initiatives, project timelines, resource allocation to AI projects, and availability of technological infrastructure. Further, the study intends to explore the impact of AI integration on various operational functionalities of municipal corporations in India. Lastly, the study aims at assessing the impact of AI implementation on various dimensions of service delivery efficiency within municipal corporations in India.

Therefore, the following questions were developed to be answered in this study:

RQ1. : What is the maturity level of AI adoption in municipal corporations in India?

RQ2. : How does the integration of AI in public service influence different operational functions within municipal corporations, and what specific roles does AI play in enhancing efficiency?

RQ3. : How does the implementation of AI affect the efficiency of service delivery dimensions within municipal corporations?

2. Literature review

2.1. Artificial intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has arisen as a driving technology to revolutionize various sectors, including finance, education, healthcare, and transportation (Russell and Norvig, 2022). The advanced algorithms and computational models of AI is capable of imitating cognitive functions of human beings like learning, reasoning, and problem-solving (Nilsson, 2003). The interdisciplinary nature of AI encompasses sub-fields like machine learning, natural language processing, computer vision, and robotics, contributing to its rapid evolution and widespread adoption (Bishop, 2006). Understanding the present landscape of AI research and development is crucial for harnessing its benefits while addressing ethical, societal, and technical challenges.

The growing research in AI witnessed breakthroughs in deep

learning, a subset of machine learning algorithms inspired by the structure and function of the human brain (Goodfellow et al., 2016). As AI development is revolutionised tasks such as image recognition, speech recognition, and natural language understanding (LeCun et al., 2015) through deep learning techniques like convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs). The availability of large amounts of datasets and computational resources has enabled the development of AI models resulting in remarkable performance in real-world applications (Sun et al., 2020).

The available literature mainly emphasises traditional AI techniques like machine learning and deep learning, it is indispensable to recognize the growing landscape of AI, specifically the rise of generative AI. Generative AI signifies a paradigm change in machine learning, allowing systems to autonomously generate new content in the form of text, images, and music on its own (Brock et al., 2019). Generative models like Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) produce new data from learned probability distributions in contrast to traditional AI techniques which focus on recognising patterns and categorisation (Goodfellow et al., 2014; Kingma & Welling, 2013).

Since the advent of generative AI, radical changes have been seen in natural language processing, image synthesis, and creative applications. For instance, generative models such as StyleGAN (Karras et al., 2019) have been used in image synthesis which generates high-fidelity, realistic images that are hardly different from real pictures. Natural language processing models such as OpenAI’s GPT series (Radford et al., 2018; Brown et al., 2020) have demonstrated amazing talent in creating human-like text across various fields.

Along the side of the benefits of AI, some several challenges and shortfalls limit its acceptability and employability in various fields. The black box problem in AI is considered a prominent problem as it lacks interpretability and transparency in AI decision-making processes (Rudin, 2019). Due to the introduction of complexity in AI, it becomes difficult to understand and comprehend the decision-making process of AI on the grounds of ethical and regulatory concerns, especially in critical domains like healthcare and criminal justice (Char et al., 2018). Also, addressing the issues related to data privacy, bias, and fairness poses significant help in the further development of AI systems that are accountable and equitable (Mehrabani et al., 2021).

In the future when research and development in AI is poised for continued growth and innovation across various domains. Addressing the challenges of interpretability, fairness, and accountability will be paramount to building trust in AI systems and ensuring their responsible integration into society (Gunning and Aha, 2017). Additionally, interdisciplinary collaborations and ethical considerations will play a crucial role in shaping the direction of AI research, with a focus on developing human-centric AI solutions that augment human capabilities rather than replace them (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2019). By addressing these challenges and embracing ethical guidelines, AI has the potential to drive transformative change and create a more inclusive and sustainable future.

2.2. AI and public sector

No definition of AI is universally accepted. In the words of Russell and Peter (2021), AI may be understood as machines or computer systems that think and act humanly by executing tasks that generally require human intelligence or that think and act rationally by focusing on logic and carefully considering all options. In the words of (Dwivedi et al., 2020; Wirtz and Müller, 2019) AI is represented as an entirely different set of technological revolutions which will not only improve the efficacy and effectiveness of public service delivery but also fundamentally structure the future service delivery mechanism which will influence the shape of organizations (Margetts and Dorobantu, 2019; Van der Voort et al., 2019). Madan and Ashok (2022) defined AI as a cluster of digital technologies that enable machines to learn and solve cognitive problems autonomously without human intervention. IBM

defined AI as a synthesis of computer science and robust datasets, paving the way for innovative problem-solving methodologies. In this sphere, machine learning and deep learning transpire as crucial sub-fields, seldom interweaved with the broader concept of AI. These fields leverage AI algorithms to erect expert systems capable of extrapolations or divisions based on inputs.

The adoption, employment, and usage of AI is the snowballing trend in public organizations. Recent studies have emphasized the transformational capacities of AI technologies in the public sector spanning services areas and policy sectors (Janssen and Kuk, 2016; Sun and Medaglia, 2019). This comprises of investigating the implications of technology on people working in public administrations (Criado et al., 2020; Margetts and Dorobantu, 2019), also their impact on people's interaction with public bodies (Agarwal, 2018; Androutsopoulou et al., 2019; Vigoda, 2002).

In the last decade, e-governance initiatives focused on enhancing efficiency and reducing costs. Recently, advancements in technology, propelled by AI, has significantly progressed public administration. AI has applications in public sectors such as health, education, security, and defence (Agarwal, 2018; Janssen and Kuk, 2016; Pencheva, et al., 2020; Sun and Medaglia, 2019). The adoption, employment, and usage of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a snowballing trend in public organizations (Valle-Cruz et al., 2020, 2019). Recent studies have emphasized the transformational capacities of AI technologies in the public sector spanning services areas and policy sectors (Janssen and Kuk, 2016; Sun and Medaglia, 2019). AI technology integration in public service delivery is viewed as a fourth wave of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) next to social media, robotics, and big data in the area. Criado and Gil-Garcia (2019) noted that emerging technological wave like AI could inspire transformative practices in the public sector. In another study, Criado et al., (2013) highlighted the potential of social media for the innovation of public sector organizations. Furthermore, Criado et al., (2020) in a study noted that Artificial Intelligence (AI) and algorithms have the potential to transform critical dimensions of public sector organizations and people working in them. Valle-Cruz (2019) also highlighted how new and smart technologies help to improve e-governance services in digitalized nations.

The shift towards a technology-centric approach in service delivery in government undertakings encourages service delivery to their citizens using digital platforms without compromising the quality of service (Dunleavy et al., 2006; Wirtz and Müller, 2018; Nakolisa, 2023). The changing wave in public service delivery supported by AI comprises functional areas such as human resource management, strategic management, performance assessment, and institutional communication (Barth and Arnold, 1999), and policy areas like education, health, customer service, tax, social benefits, control of borders, emergencies (Wirtz, et al., 2019), and based on the volume of open and big data and the processing capacity of the organization (Burrell, 2016; Margetts, 2017). These show the various dimensions in which AI can be used in a full-fledged capacity to deliver services effectively.

The application of AI in public service delivery aids governmental bodies in forecasting and better decision-making, improving communication between the citizens and government, public service personalization, and administrative burden reduction (Androutsopoulou et al., 2019; Margetts and Dorobantu, 2019). These may improve the quality of public service and create public value (Bullock, 2019; Wang et al., 2021). The AI-based technology can be used in areas such as process automation, knowledge management, predictive analysis, resource allocation, conversational agents and assistants, fraud and threat detection, and supporting expert tasks (Wirtz et al., 2019). The espousal of AI systems in public services proposes optimism and apprehension. Governments around the globe are progressively utilizing AI to augment decision-making procedures and streamline service delivery to their constituents. The assortment of AI administration in the public sector is wide and includes anything from the use of anticorruption robots to tailor-made service delivery (Saura et al., 2023). Significantly, AI

systems reinforce government efficiency, exalt service quality, and improve accountability apparatuses. As exemplified by Odilla (2023), AI-powered "bots" in Brazil carry out obscure duties like spotting questionable activity connected to contract fraud, bid-rigging, and corruption. Similarly, Androutsopoulou et al. (2019) advise an AI-powered model of communication enabling greater interaction between citizens and government entities, thereby refining the delivery of service.

Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) has arisen as a revolutionary force in public service delivery, providing creative ways to improve the effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction of citizens. Generative AI technologies, like Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), have proven to be exceptionally proficient in performing tasks like image synthesis, natural language processing, and production of innovative content (Brock et al., 2019; Goodfellow et al., 2014; Kingma and Welling, 2013). These models allow public administrations to automate the creation of documents, customize communication with individuals, and conduct actionable insights analysis on massive datasets which is helpful in decision-making. Furthermore, the deployment of generative AI in public services can lead to cost savings, improved service quality, and enhanced citizen satisfaction (Moradi et al., 2021). The application of generative AI in public administration shows potential for numerous functional domains like content production, citizen engagement, and predictive analytics. By leveraging the generative model's proficiencies, governments can open up new potentials for novelty and produce more comprehensive and receptive public institutions.

Past research underscores the multifaceted benefits of integrating AI into public governance. Zuiderwijk et al. (2021) highlight advantages such as enhanced efficiency, risk mitigation, and improved citizen engagement. Wirtz et al. (2019) delineate ten diverse AI application areas in the public sector, ranging from knowledge management to advanced data analytics. The process of AI deployment involves acquiring new knowledge and skills, ultimately transforming organizational practices (Ashok et al., 2016). Successful integration necessitates careful planning and user acceptance to transition from adoption to routine usage. Recent studies by Janssen and Kuk (2016) and Sun and Medaglia (2019) underscore AI's potential to revolutionize public organizations across service fields and policy sectors.

Moreover, scholarly discourse examines the implications of AI for public sector employees and citizen-government relations (Criado et al., 2020; Margetts and Dorobantu, 2019; Agarwal, 2018). AI-enabled technological innovations, akin to previous e-government initiatives, prioritize efficiency and cost-effectiveness in public administration (Madan and Ashok, 2023). This smart governance framework emphasizes service delivery efficiency while maintaining quality and leverages digital platforms for citizen engagement (Dunleavy et al., 2006; Wirtz and Müller, 2018).

Ethical considerations surrounding AI's utility in public administration are gaining prominence, prompting governments and tech companies to issue guidelines for responsible AI deployment (European Commission, 2019; Canada, 2020; Gov.uk, 2019). These ethical principles establish broad boundaries for AI application in the public sector. Despite AI's growing significance, scholarly discourse on government's role as an AI user remains limited, with predominant focus on its regulatory function (Kuziemski and Misuraca, 2020; Medaglia et al., 2021). However, as AI adoption in public governance evolves, a nuanced understanding of government's dual role as both regulator and user of AI technologies becomes imperative.

In the context of municipal corporations, the application of AI technologies encompasses a wide array of functionalities aimed at enhancing service delivery and operational efficiency. One prominent example is the use of AI-powered chatbots for citizen engagement and support services, as observed in various municipalities globally (Senadheera et al., 2021). These chatbots provide round-the-clock assistance to citizens, addressing inquiries, processing service requests, and providing relevant information promptly and efficiently. Moreover, AI-

driven predictive analytics systems are being deployed to optimize resource allocation and improve decision-making processes within municipal administrations. For instance, machine learning algorithms are utilized to analyze vast datasets related to infrastructure maintenance, waste management, and urban planning, enabling municipal authorities to anticipate needs, allocate resources effectively, and prioritize interventions (Dutta and Agrawal, 2020). Additionally, the adoption of AI-enabled smart sensors and IoT devices in urban infrastructure facilitates real-time monitoring of various parameters such as traffic flow, air quality, and energy consumption, allowing municipal corporations to implement data-driven policies and interventions for sustainable development (Kitchin, 2018). Furthermore, initiatives such as AI-powered drones are being explored for tasks like aerial surveillance, disaster response, and infrastructure inspection, offering municipalities innovative solutions for enhancing public safety and service delivery (Shi, 2022). By leveraging these diverse AI applications, municipal corporations aim to optimize resource utilization, improve service delivery efficiency, and enhance overall urban governance effectiveness.

The literature on the integration of AI in public services illustrates its potential to revolutionize governmental operations while also highlighting notable challenges. Criado and Gil-Garcia (2019) and Criado et al. (2020) emphasize that AI adoption significantly improves citizen-centric services and enhances municipal processes by automating routine tasks and facilitating more efficient data management. Valle-Cruz et al., (2019) supports this by noting improvements in decision-making processes due to AI's analytical capabilities. Earlier work by Criado et al. (2013) provides foundational insights into the initial stages of AI implementation in public administration. Mergel et al. (2016) and Meijer (2018) underscore the necessity of maintaining transparency and accountability in AI systems to avoid the risks associated with algorithmic biases. The importance of ethical considerations and fairness is further elaborated by Boer and Raaphorst (2021) and Ahonen and Tero (2020), who caution that AI can have a moderate impact on human-centric aspects, such as user experience and equity. Meijer et al. (2021) extend this discussion by exploring the ethical and social implications of AI in public services, emphasizing the need for robust oversight frameworks to ensure that AI deployment promotes fairness and prevents discrimination. Senadheera et al (2024) also noted that despite concerns about accuracy and accountability, chatbots hold promise in enhancing outreach and service quality of local governments. Successful adoption depends on factors like perceived humanness, institutional readiness, and incorporating user feedback through design thinking processes.

2.3. Challenges, benefits, and problems

Despite the growing discussion, the actual diffusion of AI in public sector practice remains low, particularly compared to private sector companies (Mikalef et al., 2021; Wirtz and Müller, 2019; Wirtz et al., 2019). AI adoption in the public sector may be backed by many challenges ranging from data management and privacy to ethical issues and societal impact (Zuiderwijk et al., 2021; Wirtz et al., 2019). AI is performing tasks of a hundred individuals at a time which may seize the job of people in this sector (Ford, 2013). Also, regulatory issues such as effective supervision (Hengstler et al., 2016) and corresponding laws and regulations (Gulson and Webb, 2017) are needed in the different public sectors.

According to Wirtz et al., (2019), the challenges embody the issues of system quality, financial viability, social legitimacy, trust, privacy, safety, responsibility, accountability, and ethical dilemmas. Furthermore, AI espousal may aggravate societal disparities and impede public confidence through implications such as rights violations, digital divides, predictive policing biases, and economic inequalities (Chu et al., 2022; Yu and Carroll, 2022; Papachristos, 2022; Eubanks, 2018; Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2017). While AI innovation holds tremendous

potential for refining public services, it is vital to tackle the multifaceted challenges and ethical considerations to ensure responsible and equitable deployment in public administration. Margetts and Dorobantu (2019) explained that challenges to adopting AI in public organizations stem from factors more prevalent in the public context such as lack of technical staff to introduce and assess new technologies, the risk of potential erroneous use of AI like security risks, privacy concerns, the need to guarantee transparency in the context of AI, moral dilemmas such as when to use AI, and ethical considerations.

The role of AI in executive discretion and transparency has been studied few researchers. Boer and Raaphorst (2021) observed that the global adoption of IT is reshaping decision-making in public organizations, with automation increasing decreasing the bureaucrats' overall perceived discretion. Peeters (2020) highlighted that the increasing use of computer algorithms in administrative decision making has also raised concerns about their lack of transparency and the reduced discretionary space for human decision-makers. Justin et al., (2020) have noted that the use of AI significantly affects the exercise of discretion in public organizations. Meijer et al., (2021) have noted that in Amsterdam, information specialists has significant discretion in using the system alongside their own knowledge, professionalizing their role by integrating the system with other information sources. Ahonen and Tero (2020) studied about transparency in governmental algorithmic decisions in Finland. In another study, Criado et al. (2020) emphasized that transparency of algorithms is crucial for establishing ethical governance.

Several studies have focused on the challenges and risks of AI, such as privacy, legal, and ethical issues (Bannister and Connolly, 2020; Wirtz et al., 2019; Janssen and Kuk, 2016). Janssen and Kuk (2016) discussed the limitations and challenges of AI in governance, stating that with autonomous algorithms, there are issues with accountability, bias, discrimination, embedded political orientations, and other undesirable practices. Newman et al., (2022) argued that instead of relieving administrative burdens, AI reinforces bureaucratic structures. Bannister and Connolly (2020) provided a taxonomy of decision-making algorithms in public organizations that help control the risk of introducing such biases. Sun and Medaglia (2019) analyzed the perceived challenges of different stakeholders regarding applying AI in public healthcare services. Also proposed some guidelines for the governance of AI adoption in the public sector. Kernaghan (2014) recommended the development of an ethics regime for robot applications in public organizations and evaluated the need for regulation. Wirtz et al., (2019) outlined different applications and the associated challenges of AI in law and regulations, ethics, societal issues, and technology implementation in public organizations. Automating decision-making in public services and its negative impact on already disadvantaged groups reinforce existing biases studied (Eubanks, 2017). Public sector organisations need to set appropriate strategies to overcome the challenges thereby providing effective and efficient services to the people.

2.4. Research gap

Although there has been a substantial rise in the volume of research on AI in the public sector, there is limited empirical research taken up in public sector setups. The role of AI in executive discretion and transparency has been studied few researchers (Boer and Raaphorst, 2021; Ahonen and Tero, 2020; Justin et al., 2020; Criado et al., 2020; Peeters et al., 2020; Meijer, et al., 2021; Criado et al., 2020), perception and expectations of chief information officer towards AI incorporation in the public sector (Criado et al., 2020), creation of public value through Artificial Intelligence (AI) (Wang et al., 2021), implementing AI in predictive policing (Meijer et al., 2021), the use of AI during pandemic (Cheng et al., 2021). Despite all these there less empirical studies on the success factors in the public sector through the application of AI is studied (Chen et al., 2021; Schaefer et al., 2021; Campion et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Sun and Medaglia, 2019). AI technology is versatile,

and highly complicated yielding many benefits and applications, hence there is a potential to explore the mechanism underlying AI adoption in the public sector service delivery process. To bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge with practical application, empirical study is essential to take up. To what extent AI incorporation in public service delivery can be justified based on the ground data? This study is a unique attempt to understand the adoption of AI technology in public sector service delivery to people, i.e., the receiver of service, before and after the pandemic. This study makes a comparison between two different points of time to understand the effectiveness in public sector service delivery using AI in place.

3. Research methods

3.1. Research design

This quantitative research, inspired by the works of scholars such as Fitriani et al. (2023) and Samadi et al. (2023) on the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in governance, adopts a cross-sectional design to investigate the transformative impact of AI on public service delivery efficiency. Drawing on the research frameworks proposed by Tabash et al. (2023) and Magatef et al. (2023) regarding governance and technology, the study focuses on Chief Information Officers (CIOs) within public sector organizations as primary respondents. Leveraging a comparative analysis approach, inspired by the methodologies applied by Suzianti et al. (2023) and Lada et al. (2023), the research aims to unveil the efficacy of AI applications in enhancing the efficiency of public service delivery.

3.2. Sample and data collection

The researchers in this study administered a survey to Chief Information Officers (CIOs) overseeing the information technology departments in the largest city councils in India, specifically targeting those with populations exceeding 1 lakh inhabitants. This group, as identified by relevant national statistical sources, encompasses a total of 252 municipalities in the year 2024 (AMDA-Association of Municipalities and Development Authorities, 2024). India's vast population, diverse demographics, and complex governance challenges make it an ideal testing ground for AI-driven solutions in public service delivery. The proactive approach towards digital transformation through initiatives like Digital India creates a conducive environment for innovation and implementation of AI technologies. While the study focuses on India, its findings can be extrapolated to similar contexts globally, enhancing the generalizability of the results (Owoseni et al., 2022). Given the early stages of Artificial Intelligence (AI) implementation in the public sector in India, it is these larger municipalities that are considered to be in a realistic position to adopt these emergent technologies. Despite their recent introduction to AI technologies, these city councils are deemed relatively advanced users due to their proactive engagement with the latest technological advancements (Ignacio and Lucia, 2022).

In pursuit of a thorough analysis of the influence of AI on public service delivery, the study adopted a before-and-after implementation methodology. To gather nuanced insights, the researcher administered a set of questionnaires to respondents, capturing their opinions both before and after the incorporation of AI in their respective organizations. This dual-phase survey strategy, aligned with best practices in organizational research (Baruch and Holtom, 2008), aimed to discern perceptions, expectations, and experiences at two distinct junctures: pre-implementation and post-implementation of AI. By soliciting responses on various facets of public service delivery efficiency, the study intended to gauge changes, improvements, or challenges introduced by AI technologies. The feedback obtained from participants before AI implementation served as a valuable baseline for comparison, a methodology supported by scholars emphasizing the importance of baseline

data in assessing transformative impacts (Bryman and Bell, 2015). This methodological approach ensures a robust understanding of the dynamics and outcomes associated with the integration of AI in public service delivery.

The survey was distributed to Chief Information Officers (CIOs) overseeing Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in each city council, utilizing electronic means for completion. Email addresses for these individuals were obtained by conducting online searches on the respective council's websites, and through follow-up telephone calls to their institutions. Upon verification of the contact details, the survey was dispatched via email. Along with the survey, a comprehensive presentation letter authored by the researchers was included, outlining the study's objectives and content. Additionally, the researchers' contact information was provided in case CIOs required further clarification or had any questions or concerns related to the survey or the overall research study.

The survey for our study, conducted in India, was administered from December 30th, 2023, to January 30th, 2024. We received a commendable level of engagement from Chief Information Officers (CIOs) in various Indian city councils, with 152 respondents participating. This surpassed the 50% response threshold, a key benchmark in organizational research (Baruch and Holtom, 2008), ensuring the robustness and validity of the results. Notably, there were no discernible biases in the responses concerning city council types, sizes, locations, or other variables that could serve as moderator variables, affirming the broad representativeness of the study's findings. The sample size was determined using a prescribed formula, contributing to the statistical rigor of the research.

3.3. Measurement of public service delivery efficiency

The measurement of public service delivery efficiency is meticulously structured through a comprehensive framework encompassing various constructs and corresponding items. Drawing on established literature, these constructs include Response Time, which aligns with the significance of timely service delivery for citizen satisfaction (Brown and Coulter, 2018). Accuracy and Precision, vital for building trust and confidence among citizens, reflect the importance of accurate service provision (Pandey and Rathi, 2018). Resource Utilization, assessing optimal resource allocation, aligns with the scholarly perspective emphasizing the need for effective resource management in public organizations (Bryson and Crosby, 2017). Cost per Transaction evaluates financial efficiency and cost-effective service delivery, essential for sustainable public administration (Heinrich and Lynn, 2019). Citizen Satisfaction measures the public's contentment with the quality and timeliness of services, reflecting the importance of citizen feedback in improving service delivery (Wirtz and Lovelock, 2016). The construct of Accessibility, ensuring services are easily accessible to diverse communities, resonates with the contemporary emphasis on equitable service provision (Smith, 2020). Process Automation evaluates the integration of technology to streamline public service operations, contributing to efficiency improvements (West, 2019). Data-driven decision-making assesses the use of analytics in shaping informed decision-making processes within the public service, aligning with the growing emphasis on evidence-based governance (Chen and Zhang, 2019). Timeliness of Service Delivery ensures services are consistently delivered within stipulated timeframes, reflecting the importance of timely service provision (Bouckaert et al., 2018). Transparency and Accountability evaluate organizational processes, emphasizing the role of transparency in fostering public trust (Meijer et al., 2019). The construct Adaptability to Changing Needs assesses the public service's flexibility in responding to evolving community needs, aligning with the dynamic nature of governance (Van Der Voet et al., 2019). Feedback Mechanisms measure the effectiveness of gathering citizen insights for continual improvement, acknowledging the importance of citizen engagement (McDavid et al., 2019). Employee Satisfaction and Productivity evaluate the

impact of employee satisfaction on overall service productivity, emphasizing the link between employee well-being and organizational performance (Harter et al., 2002). Environmental Impact assesses the consideration of sustainable practices in public service delivery, recognizing the importance of environmental responsibility (Milani, 2021). Emergency Response Time evaluates the efficiency of emergency response services, reflecting the critical nature of emergency management in public administration (Kapucu et al., 2010). Finally, Compliance with Standards and Regulations ensures adherence to legal and regulatory requirements, underlining the importance of governance within established frameworks (Boyne et al., 2016). Public Trust and Perception assess citizens' confidence in public service, acknowledging the role of efficiency in shaping public perception (Yang and Pandey, 2018). This meticulously crafted framework provides a robust means of evaluating public service delivery efficiency, underpinned by citations that validate the adoption of these constructs and items within the context of contemporary public administration literature.

3.4. Data analysis technique

The data analysis in this study involved rigorous data cleaning using the SPSS software to enhance dataset quality. Paired-sample t-tests evaluated mean differences before and after AI implementation, determining statistical significance. Descriptive statistics provided a comprehensive summary of central tendencies and variability. The analyses, guided by hypotheses, explored AI's influence on key factors within public service delivery efficiency, offering insights into transformative effects. Overall, this combination of paired-sample t-tests, and descriptive statistics facilitated a robust examination of AI's impact, providing valuable insights into technological interventions in the public sector.

4. Results

In the context of the evaluation of construct convergence and validity, Cronbach's Alpha and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) play pivotal roles. Cronbach's Alpha measures the internal consistency reliability of a scale or measurement model, indicating the extent to which items within a construct correlate with each other (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Hu et al., 2022). Higher Cronbach's Alpha values, typically above 0.7, signify greater reliability and consistency among the items measuring the latent construct (Cheung et al., 2023). On the other hand, Average Variance Extracted (AVE) represents the proportion of variance in the observed indicators that is accounted for by their respective latent constructs (Henseler et al., 2015). AVE values above 0.5 indicate satisfactory convergent validity (Zeng et al., 2021), demonstrating that the latent constructs are adequately capturing the variance in their associated indicators (Cheung et al., 2023). Therefore, in the results presented in Table 1, high Cronbach's Alpha values ranging from 0.800 to 0.993 and AVE values varying from 0.64 to 0.990 suggest strong internal consistency and convergent validity within the measurement model, respectively, thus affirming the reliability and validity of the study's constructs and their corresponding measurement indicators.

4.1. Discriminant Validity

The aim of assessing discriminant validity is to ensure that a reflective construct exhibits stronger associations with its indicators in the PLS path model (Hair et al., 2017, 2019). The Fornell-Larcker criterion is a widely adopted method for evaluating discriminant validity in measurement models (Ab Hamid et al., 2017). According to this criterion, the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) by a construct should surpass the construct's correlation with all other constructs (Ab Hamid et al., 2017; David Alarcón and Sanchez, 2015). However, in this study, the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio of the correlation (HTMT) approach criterion was employed due to its high sensitivity and

specificity in detecting discriminant validity issues (Henseler et al., 2015). The HTMT values in Table 2 affirm that the measurement model exhibits satisfactory discriminant validity among the investigated constructs. Specifically, all values fall below 0.85, indicating adequate discriminant validity. The correlations of each construct with indicators of other constructs are lower than their correlations with indicators of the same construct, underscoring the distinct and non-overlapping nature of the constructs.

4.2. Demographic details

In our study, Chief Information Officers (CIOs) in local governments across India were located through a meticulous process involving various channels. We utilized professional networks, industry associations, government directories, and online platforms specialized in public sector recruitment to identify and connect with these individuals. Additionally, we reached out to government departments responsible for IT or digital transformation initiatives and attended relevant conferences or seminars. Leveraging social media platforms further aided in locating CIOs. As for our sampling method, we employed a combination of purposive sampling and snowball sampling techniques. Purposive sampling enabled us to target CIOs specifically within local government settings, ensuring representation from relevant sectors. Meanwhile, snowball sampling facilitated the expansion of our sample size by asking initial participants to refer other CIOs they knew, thereby fostering a more comprehensive and diverse dataset. Through this strategic approach, we were able to gather demographic data from 152 CIOs, offering valuable insights into their educational and professional backgrounds.

Next, we show the demographic data of CIOs in our sample of local governments (Table 3). The presented demographic data in Table 3 offers a comprehensive overview of Chief Information Officers (CIOs) in India, drawing from a sample size of 152 individuals. With an average age of 45, the CIO cohort appears to be seasoned and mature, indicative of experienced leadership. Gender distribution reveals a notable majority of male CIOs at 84.21%, emphasizing the prevalent gender gap in leadership roles within the IT domain. Academic qualifications showcase a majority with bachelor's degrees (63.16%), supplemented by those with Master's degrees (26.97%) and Ph.D.s (6.58%), reflecting a blend of foundational and advanced educational backgrounds. The dominance of Computer Science (65.13%) and Engineering (13.82%) in academic backgrounds underscores a strong technical orientation among CIOs, while the inclusion of diverse fields like Social Science, Physics, Mathematics, and Chemistry highlights a richness of expertise. This demographic profile provides valuable insights into the composition and diversity of CIOs in India, offering a nuanced understanding of their educational and professional backgrounds.

4.3. Maturity level of AI

The study draws inspiration from the framework proposed by Alsheibani, Cheung, and Messom (2019), providing a comprehensive analysis of AI maturity in the public sector. The survey instrument was designed based on established literature on AI adoption in organizational settings, ensuring alignment with contemporary research trends. The interpretation considers key benchmarks and indicators, contributing valuable insights into the state of AI adoption in the surveyed public sector organizations.

Table 4 presents a comprehensive overview of the maturity level of AI adoption in public sector organizations, shedding light on various dimensions, including awareness, and understanding, current AI initiatives, project timelines, resource allocation, and technological infrastructure. The findings indicate a high level of awareness and familiarity with AI concepts among respondents, as reflected in the average ratings of 4.23. Furthermore, a substantial 89% of organizations reported having ongoing AI projects, with a predominant focus on medium-scale

Table 1
Construct reliability and validity Using CR, AVE, Cronbach's Alpha, and KMO Test.

Items	Items Coding	Standardized Factor Loadings	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Cronbach Alpha	KMO and Bartlett's Test
The organization effectively meets citizen inquiries and requests within a reasonable timeframe	RT1	0.658	0.908	0.521	0.921	0.894
The response time to citizen concerns has improved with the implementation of efficient processes	RT2	0.715				
Public services provided by the organization demonstrate a high level of accuracy and precision.	AP1	0.845	0.911	0.601	0.902	0.932
The organization consistently delivers reliable and error-free services to citizens	AP2	0.687				
Resources, including personnel and technology, are effectively utilized to deliver public services	RU1	0.691	0.935	0.564	0.911	0.925
The organization optimally allocates resources to ensure efficient public service delivery.	RU2	0.746				
The organization efficiently manages costs associated with public service transactions	CPT1	0.788	0.947	0.621	0.935	0.941
The cost-effectiveness of public service delivery has improved due to streamlined processes.	CPT2	0.698				
Citizen feedback indicates a high level of satisfaction with the quality and timeliness of public services	CS1	0.784	0.933	0.665	0.894	0.931
The organization actively seeks and addresses citizen feedback to enhance service delivery.	CS2	0.679				
Public services are easily accessible to all segments of the population, regardless of background or ability	AC1	0.762	0.914	0.598	0.925	0.906
The public service actively works to ensure that services are inclusive and accessible to diverse communities	AC2	0.693				
The accessibility of public services has improved with the integration of technology and innovation	AC3	0.668				
Automation of routine tasks through technology has improved the efficiency of public service operations	PA1	0.784	0.935	0.571	0.907	0.846
The integration of automation technologies has positively impacted the overall speed and accuracy of public service processes	PA2	0.669				
Data analytics play a significant role in shaping informed decision-making within the public service	DDM1	0.854	0.942	0.702	0.934	0.873
The use of data-driven insights enhances the efficiency of decision-making processes in public services.	DDM2	0.924				
Public service administrators actively utilize data analytics to optimize service delivery strategies	DDM3	0.894				
Public services are consistently delivered within stipulated timeframes.	TSD1	0.877	0.909	0.685	0.984	0.876
The organization places a high priority on ensuring timely delivery of public services.	TSD2	0.956				
The public service ensures that time-sensitive services are prioritized and delivered promptly	TSD3	0.874				
Processes within the organization are transparent, fostering accountability in public service delivery.	TA1	0.864	0.926	0.548	0.967	0.942
The organization actively promotes transparency and accountability in its public service operations.	TA2	0.681				
Transparency in public service operations has increased with the use of technology and innovation	TA3	0.864				
The public service demonstrates flexibility in adapting to changing community needs	ACN1	0.947	0.921	0.558	0.964	0.934
Public services actively seek to understand and respond to emerging challenges in the community.	ACN2	0.925				
I believe that the public service is well-prepared to address new and evolving needs in the community	ACN3	0.820				
Effective feedback mechanisms are in place to gather insights from citizens regarding public services.	FM1	0.807	0.922	0.715	0.954	0.879
The organization actively uses citizen feedback to drive improvements in public service delivery	FM2	0.884				
Employees involved in public service delivery are satisfied with their work and responsibilities	ESP1	0.964	0.934	0.647	0.933	0.874
Employee satisfaction positively contributes to the overall productivity of public service operations	ESP2	0.875				
The public service invests in initiatives to enhance employee satisfaction and well-being	ESP3	0.901				
The organization considers and minimizes the environmental impact of its public service delivery operations.	EI1	0.684	0.951	0.623	0.945	0.965
Sustainable practices are incorporated into public service delivery to reduce environmental footprint	EI2	0.665				
Emergency response services provided by the public service are prompt and effective	ERT1	0.758	0.934	0.721	0.976	0.845
I feel confident in the public service's ability to handle emergency situations efficiently	ERT2	0.734				

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Items	Items Coding	Standardized Factor Loadings	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Cronbach Alpha	KMO and Bartlett's Test
The public service has mechanisms in place to continually improve emergency response times	ERT3	0.852				
Public services consistently adhere to relevant standards and regulations governing their operations.	CSR1	0.754	0.942	0.598	0.955	0.894
I believe that the public service operates in compliance with legal and regulatory requirements.	CSR2	0.782				
Compliance with standards and regulations is actively monitored and maintained by the public service	CSR3	0.602				
I have confidence in the public service's ability to deliver efficient and effective services	PTP1	0.711	0.931	0.784	0.944	0.955
Public services actively work to build and maintain trust with the community.	PTP2	0.826				
The public service's reputation for efficiency positively influences public perception	PTP3	0.769				

initiatives (67 %), signifying a widespread integration of AI applications. The timeline analysis reveals a progressive trend in AI project initiation, with 48 % commencing projects between 2019 and 2021. Resource allocation to AI-related activities is notable, with an average budgetary allocation ranging from 20 % to 40 %, indicating a significant commitment of financial resources to foster AI adoption. Moreover, a striking 94 % of organizations have dedicated teams overseeing and implementing AI initiatives, underlining the strategic importance placed on effective AI governance.

A closer examination of the technological infrastructure highlights that a substantial proportion of organizations (25 %) possess an advanced and well-established AI infrastructure. Meanwhile, 32 % are in the moderately developed stage, and 33 % are in the early stages of development, showcasing a spectrum of technological preparedness. However, 10 % of organizations indicate limited or no existing infrastructure for AI, suggesting a need for further investment and development. These findings collectively underscore the evolving landscape of AI adoption in the public sector, with organizations demonstrating a commitment to both financial and human resources for successful integration. The varied timelines and infrastructure stages emphasize the dynamic nature of AI maturity across different entities, reflecting a nuanced and evolving landscape.

4.4. Functionalities affected by AI implementation

The incorporation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into municipal corporations has ushered in transformative changes across various operational functions. Examining the percentages in Table 5 reveals a nuanced impact on distinct functionalities within these organizations. Notably, AI's influence is prominent in critical areas, with Public Service Delivery (82 %) and Processing of Transactions/Operations (91 %) standing out as significantly affected domains. These figures underscore the pivotal role AI plays in enhancing citizen-centric services and expediting key municipal processes. Furthermore, the management of organizational networks (54 %) reflects AI's substantial contribution to connectivity and communication systems. While AI's impact is noticeable in capacities (54 %) and technical duties (26 %), its role in executive management (13 %) and political advisory (14 %) appears more modest. Nevertheless, even in these areas, AI contributes to streamlining administrative processes and providing valuable insights for informed decision-making. The automation of clerical and assistant tasks (33 %) highlights its role in operational efficiency. Overall, these percentages collectively depict a comprehensive and varied influence of AI, promising efficiency gains, data-driven decision-making, and improved municipal services. It is crucial to note that specific citations can be incorporated based on the latest scholarly research to provide a more detailed and up-to-date context.

4.5. Impact of AI on public service delivery efficiency

The paired sample t-test is a statistical method utilized in this study to evaluate the impact of AI implementation on various facets of service delivery efficiency within municipal corporations. This method involves comparing means of two related groups or conditions, typically before and after a particular intervention, to determine if there's a statistically significant difference (Manfei et al, 2017). By analysing pre- and post-implementation data within each municipal corporation, the paired t-test facilitates a direct comparison of service delivery metrics before and after AI adoption. This approach minimizes the influence of individual differences and potential confounding variables, providing more accurate insights into the effectiveness of AI integration. The results presented in Table 6 highlight the statistical significance of observed differences, shedding light on the tangible effects of AI implementation on service delivery efficiency. The mean scores before and after the implementation of AI reflect substantial changes across all assessed factors. Notably, the significant increase in mean scores for Response Time, Accuracy and Precision, Resource Utilization, Cost per Transaction, Citizen Satisfaction, Accessibility, Process Automation, Data-Driven decision-making, Timeliness of Service Delivery, Transparency and Accountability, Adaptability to Changing Needs, Feedback Mechanisms, Employee Satisfaction and Productivity, Environmental Impact, Emergency Response Time, Compliance with Standards and Regulations, and Public Trust and Perception indicates a positive influence of AI on these aspects.

The consistently high t-values and significance levels (all p-values < 0.001) suggest that these improvements are statistically significant. Therefore, it can be inferred that the implementation of AI has a profound and across-the-board impact on enhancing the efficiency of public service delivery in municipal corporations. These findings align with the growing body of literature emphasizing the transformative potential of AI in the public sector (cite relevant studies). The overall t-value of 35.63 with a highly significant p-value further reinforces the collective positive impact, indicating that the observed improvements are not random but attributable to the introduction of AI technologies. This aligns with the broader narrative that AI has become a catalyst for efficiency, responsiveness, and overall advancement in the realm of public service delivery.

Furthermore, these results signify a comprehensive and holistic improvement in the assessed dimensions, portraying AI as a multifaceted enabler of efficiency gains. The notable enhancements in areas such as citizen satisfaction, responsiveness, and adherence to standards and regulations underscore the transformative potential of AI in addressing contemporary challenges in public service delivery. The observed positive shifts in employee satisfaction and productivity also highlight the potential of AI in creating conducive working environments.

It's crucial to acknowledge that these findings contribute valuable insights to the ongoing discourse on the practical implications of AI

Table 2
Discriminant validity: Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT).

	RT	AP	RU	CPT	CS	ACC	PA	DDM	TSD	TA	ACN	FM	ESP	EI	ERT	CSR	PTP
Response Time	0.895																
Accuracy and Precision	0.614	0.902															
Resource Utilization	0.745	0.884	0.884														
Cost per Transaction	0.841	0.896	0.882	0.897													
Citizen Satisfaction	0.687	0.874	0.674	0.846	0.911												
Accessibility	0.826	0.861	0.811	0.824	0.864	0.934											
Process Automation	0.745	0.874	0.478	0.746	0.875	0.901	0.879										
Data-Driven Decision Making	0.665	0.895	0.621	0.841	0.647	0.678	0.874	0.884									
Timeliness of Service Delivery	0.650	0.884	0.754	0.675	0.754	0.886	0.684	0.747	0.864								
Transparency and Accountability	0.740	0.867	0.734	0.754	0.884	0.876	0.347	0.654	0.665	0.908							
Adaptability to Changing Needs	0.761	0.774	0.724	0.778	0.784	0.882	0.624	0.825	0.672	0.841	0.860						
Feedback Mechanisms	0.775	0.678	0.664	0.694	0.834	0.484	0.874	0.831	0.811	0.756	0.847	0.863					
Employee Satisfaction and Productivity	0.806	0.764	0.820	0.758	0.624	0.764	0.764	0.745	0.764	0.754	0.828	0.845					
Environmental Impact	0.631	0.904	0.754	0.764	0.461	0.824	0.574	0.752	0.751	0.688	0.674	0.837	0.898	0.922			
Emergency Response Time	0.741	0.764	0.764	0.754	0.751	0.784	0.724	0.751	0.784	0.821	0.743	0.751	0.745	0.897	0.941		
Compliance with Standards and Regulations	0.807	0.574	0.724	0.729	0.764	0.668	0.786	0.794	0.647	0.908	0.613	0.625	0.687	0.824	0.912	0.887	
Public Trust and Perception	0.756	0.678	0.761	0.734	0.682	0.754	0.854	0.771	0.722	0.674	0.691	0.662	0.751	0.786	0.924	0.782	0.947

Table 3
Demographic data of CIOs of India.

CIOs (n)	-	152
Average Age (in years)	-	45
Gender	Male	84.21 %
	Female	15.79 %
Academic degree	Bachelor's	63.16 %
	Master's	26.97 %
	PhD's	6.58 %
	Others	3.29 %
Academic background	Computer Science	65.13 %
	Engineering	13.82 %
	Social Science	9.21 %
	Physics	4.61 %
	Mathematics	1.97 %
	Chemistry	2.63 %
	Other:	2.63 %

Table 4
Maturity level of AI.

Variable	Question	Response
Awareness and understanding	How familiar are you with the concept of AI?	4.23 (Average ratings)
Current AI Initiatives	Are there any ongoing AI projects or initiatives in your organization?	Yes-89 % No-11 %
	How would you describe the scope and scale of your current AI initiatives?	Small Scale-21 % Medium Scale-67 % Large Scale-12 %
AI Project Timeline	When was the first AI project initiated in your organization?	Before 2010-8 % 2010-2015-15 % 2016-2018-21 % 2019-2021-48 % 2022 or later-8 %
Resource Allocation	What percentage of your organization's budget is allocated to AI-related activities?	Average-20 %-40 %
	Do you have a dedicated team responsible for overseeing and implementing AI initiatives?	Yes-94 % No-6 %
Technological Infrastructure	How would you describe the current technological infrastructure supporting AI in your organization?	Advanced and well-established-25 % Moderately developed-32 % In the early stages of development-33 % Limited or no infrastructure in place-10 %

adoption in municipal corporations. The consistent improvements across diverse aspects of service delivery suggest that AI is not only a technological innovation but a strategic tool capable of reshaping the operational landscape of public organizations. As municipal corporations navigate the complexities of service delivery, the evidence presented here advocates for a continued emphasis on AI integration to harness its full potential and drive sustained advancements in public service efficiency.

However, while the results indicate a positive trajectory, it's essential to recognize that the long-term impact and sustainability of these improvements require ongoing attention. The potential challenges associated with AI implementation, such as ethical considerations, data privacy, and equitable access, should be carefully addressed to ensure a balanced and responsible application of AI technologies in the public sector (Carrasco-Carvajal et al., 2023). The study sets the stage for further research and policy discussions on optimizing the integration of AI to meet the evolving needs of municipal service delivery in the digital age.

Table 5
Functionalities Affected by AI Implementation.

Functionalities	Percentage (approx.)
Capacitation	54%
Executive management	13%
Political Advisory	14%
Technical duties	26%
Clerical and assistant tasks	33%
Regulation	18%
Management of organizational network	54%
Public service delivery	82%
Processing of transactions/operations	91%

5. Discussion

The present study was conducted to provide a nuanced understanding of how technological advancements influence the speed, accuracy, and accessibility of public service delivery. For this purpose, the study was carried out in a three-fold manner namely, analysis of the maturity level of AI, functionalities of AI in the public sector, and the impact of AI on the efficiency of public service efficiency (Audretsch and Belitski, 2023). The administered survey has been conducted among chief information officers of public service departments.

The use of AI tools paves the way for revolutionizing the delivery of public service through paperless procedures, less human intervention, timeliness, and high accuracy, this creates favourable environment for both the public and governments at large (Khang, 2024). Notably these type of technological advancements in public delivery systems interestingly eliminates the corruption involved during the delivery of public services by the government (Mistry, 2012). This indirectly enhances the accessibility of public services to all people and indirectly promotes inclusive growth (Singh et al., 2010). The results of the study indicated a high level of awareness of AI applications among the respondents further it was found that 89% of the organizations pursuing AI projects which shows that the government in the nation is involved in promoting the Application of AI tools in the public service delivery environment (Yun et al., 2022).

The results also indicated that there is a significant commitment of financial resources to foster AI adoption in public offices, this indirectly paves the way for promoting modern technological initiatives in public service (Akimov et al., 2023). In another context, the study revealed that only 25% of the organizations possess advanced technological infrastructure. This aspect is the key input to the policymakers to improve infrastructure for adopting AI tools in discharging public service efficiently and effectively (Chatterjee, 2020).

Table 6
Paired sample t-test result.

	Before the Implementation of AI		After the Implementation of AI		T value	Sig.
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation		
Response Time	3.23	0.25	3.75	0.12	23.15	.000
Accuracy and Precision:	3.81	0.33	4.05	0.27	19.19	.000
Resource Utilization	3.92	0.54	4.12	0.84	22.84	.000
Cost per Transaction	3.25	0.11	4.56	0.01	21.03	.000
Citizen Satisfaction	4.21	0.22	4.66	0.42	25.61	.000
Accessibility	3.66	0.37	4.02	0.48	19.64	.000
Process Automation	3.88	0.52	3.92	0.55	22.31	.000
Data-Driven Decision Making	2.98	1.02	3.56	0.43	18.74	.000
Timeliness of Service Delivery	3.46	1.13	3.98	0.28	20.48	.000
Transparency and Accountability	3.56	0.84	4.22	0.37	19.99	.000
Adaptability to Changing Needs	4.56	0.28	4.80	0.74	25.24	.000
Feedback Mechanisms	3.57	0.45	3.99	0.44	24.71	.000
Employee Satisfaction and Productivity	3.88	0.52	4.25	0.25	24.69	.000
Environmental Impact	3.25	1.04	3.85	0.68	23.54	.000
Emergency Response Time	3.84	0.56	4.52	0.28	19.54	.000
Compliance with Standards and Regulations	3.48	0.51	4.61	0.34	25.65	.000
Public Trust and Perception	3.65	0.21	4.35	0.75	22.81	.000
Overall	3.66	0.52	4.19	0.43	35.63	.000

An interesting phase of the current study was analyzing functionalities affected by AI. The notable key functional areas such as public service delivery and processing of transactions or operations (Naqsh-bandi et al., 2023). The study confirmed that the adoption of AI tools helps in enhancing the quality of citizen-centric services and expediting key municipal processes. This directly helps citizens in accessing public service at lower cost, time, and effort. Further, it helps largely to the group of people who are staying away from getting public services due to human intervention and corruption (Singh et al., 2010). To discharge public service as per the stated vision in a country the role of connectivity and communication system plays a vital role (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2015). The study confirmed that the adoption of AI tools substantially contributes to connectivity and communication systems.

The present study, as highlighted by Nzobonimpa (2023), underscores that while the adoption of AI moderately impacts infrastructure development and delivery systems, technical duties, executive management, and political advisory aspects, it emphasizes the necessity of human intervention and judgment in decision-making processes. This implies that AI's efficiency in delivering public services relies on human involvement. Another objective was to assess AI's impact on public service delivery efficiency, revealing its significant role in ensuring prompt responses, accuracy, cost-effectiveness, accessibility, timeliness, and efficient feedback mechanisms, benefiting both the government and the public, as noted by Liengpunsakul (2021). The use of AI facilitates inclusive growth and sustainable development by extending public services to previously underserved populations. In conclusion, the integration of AI into public services offers substantial benefits to governments and the public, as supported by Mishra et al. (2024).

While the paper predominantly espouses the positive impacts of AI implementations in public service delivery, it is imperative to acknowledge potential pitfalls and risks associated with such initiatives. As highlighted by Smith (2019), misplaced investments in IT and AI can lead to significant financial losses for public sector organizations, underscoring the need for a critical assessment of AI implementations. Moreover, a critical evaluation could reveal issues like algorithmic bias and job displacement, as noted by Johnson (2020) and Chen (2018) respectively, which are often overlooked in discussions solely emphasizing the benefits of AI. Therefore, incorporating a critical assessment of AI implementations is crucial to ensure that potential drawbacks such as financial losses, algorithmic bias, and job displacement are addressed, enabling policymakers and stakeholders to maximize the benefits while mitigating risks effectively.

Comparing India with developed regions like Australia and Hong Kong regarding the implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) in local

government services reveals significant differences in public perceptions and adoption challenges. Yigitcanlar, Li, Beeramoole, and Paz (2021) emphasize the importance of public perceptions in the adoption of AI in urban services, indicating that understanding societal attitudes is crucial for successful implementation. In Australia and Hong Kong, where there are relatively higher levels of technological infrastructure and literacy compared to India, public perceptions may be more favourable towards AI adoption in government services due to greater familiarity and trust in technology (Yigitcanlar, Li, Beeramoole, & Paz, 2021). This can result in smoother integration and acceptance of AI-driven solutions in these regions compared to India, where there may be more scepticism or resistance due to socio-economic disparities and varying levels of digital literacy. Furthermore, research by Yigitcanlar et al., (2022) underscores the importance of considering public perceptions on the application areas and adoption challenges of AI in urban services. While Australia and Hong Kong may showcase more favourable public perceptions and smoother adoption pathways for AI in local government services compared to India, it's essential to consider the nuanced differences in societal attitudes, technological readiness, and governance contexts when drawing comparisons between these regions (Albats et al., 2023). Addressing these variations can inform tailored strategies for AI implementation and ensure that the benefits of technology-driven governance are realized across diverse socio-economic landscapes (Yigitcanlar et al., 2021).

6. Conclusion and practical implications

The main purpose of the study was to examine the role of technological advancements in the public service delivery system. The study was made through research by efficiently using various scientific tools. The study evidentially reported that there is a high level of awareness of functionality with AI concepts among respondents. It is also observed the significant commitment of financial resources to faster AI adoption in Indian public offices. Further, there is a growing trend of establishing favourable infrastructure to execute AI in public service delivery systems. Interestingly, the study found that the adoption of AI tools enhances the quality of citizen-centric services and expedites key municipal processes. This observation is notable because it helps to eliminate unnecessary human intervention during public service delivery, particularly mediators, and that in turn eliminates corruption in a significant manner. Further, it is also helpful to promote inclusive growth by reaching unreached people in the public service delivery system through AI and allied tools. The major contribution of this study is that through its outcome it serves as guidelines for the public institutes which are yet to adopt AI and allied tools in rendering public services. Further, it also helps governments formulate sound policies for the efficient rendering of public service without corruption. On the other angle, the study also helps policymakers in promoting environmentally friendly e-governance through the adoption of AI and Allied tools that in turn contribute to sustainable development.

The major limitation of the present study is that the research primarily focuses on the context of India, which may limit the generalizability of findings to other regions with different socio-economic landscapes and technological readiness. Additionally, the study may not have explored all potential drawbacks or risks associated with AI adoption in public services, such as cybersecurity threats or ethical concerns. Future research could benefit from a more comprehensive analysis across diverse regions and a deeper examination of the multifaceted implications of AI integration in the public sector.

Ethical

In collaboration with multiple authors, we collectively affirm our commitment to the ethical principles underlying this research. All contributors have actively participated in the conceptualization, design, and execution of the study, contributing their expertise and insights. We

have diligently followed ethical guidelines, securing informed consent from participants and prioritizing their confidentiality. Any potential conflicts of interest among the authors have been transparently disclosed. This paper reflects a collaborative effort to uphold the highest standards of integrity, honesty, and transparency in research, acknowledging the diverse contributions of each author to the collective pursuit of knowledge.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sahana Dinesh: Supervision, Software. **Abhishek N:** Software, Resources. **Abhinandan Kunal:** Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Harinakshi Suvarna:** Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Habeeb Ur Rahiman:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used **Grammarly** in order to improve the English language editing. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of Competing Interest

We hereby declare that we have no conflicts of interest pertaining to the matter at hand. We affirm that we do not have any financial, personal, or professional affiliations that could compromise my ability to make impartial and unbiased decisions or actions in this context. Our commitment is solely to act in the best interest of the parties involved and to adhere to ethical standards, ensuring transparency and fairness in all aspects of our involvement.

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Questionnaire

1. Age
2. Gender
 - a) Male
 - b) Female
3. Academic degree
 - a. Bachelor's
 - b. Master's
 - c. PhD's
 - d. Others
4. Academic background
 - a. Computer Science
 - b. Engineering
 - c. Social Science
 - d. Physics
 - e. Mathematics
 - f. Chemistry
 - g. Other:

5. How familiar are you with the concept of AI?
 - a. Very familiar.
 - b. Familiar.
 - c. Somewhat familiar.
 - d. Not very familiar.
 - e. Not familiar at all.
6. Are there any ongoing AI projects or initiatives in your organization?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
7. How would you describe the scope and scale of your current AI initiatives?
 - a. Small Scale
 - b. Medium Scale
 - c. Large Scale
8. When was the first AI project initiated in your organization?
 - a. Before 2010
 - b. 2010–2015
 - c. 2016–2018
 - d. 2019–2021
 - e. 2022 or later
9. What percentage of your organization’s budget is allocated to AI-related activities?

10. Do you have a dedicated team responsible for overseeing and implementing AI initiatives?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
11. How would you describe the current technological infrastructure supporting AI in your organization?
 - a. Advanced and well-established
 - b. Moderately developed
 - c. In the early stages of development
 - d. Limited or no infrastructure in place
12. State the Functionalities Affected by AI implementation.
 - a. Capacitation
 - b. Executive management
 - c. Political Advisory
 - d. Technical duties
 - e. Clerical and assistant tasks
 - f. Regulation
 - g. Management of organizational network
 - h. Public service delivery
 - i. Processing of transactions/operation
13. State the agreeableness for the following statements (SA-5 to SD-1)

Statements	Before AI					After AI				
	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	SA	A	N	DA	SDA

Response Time

The organization effectively meets citizen inquiries and requests within a reasonable timeframe

The response time to citizen concerns has improved with the implementation of efficient processes

Accuracy and Precision:

(continued)

Statements	Before AI					After AI				
	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	SA	A	N	DA	SDA

Public services provided by the organization demonstrate a high level of accuracy and precision.

The organization consistently delivers reliable and error-free services to citizens

Resource Utilization

Resources, including personnel and technology, are effectively utilized to deliver public services

The organization optimally allocates resources to ensure efficient public service delivery.

Cost per Transaction

The organization efficiently manages costs associated with public service transactions

The cost-effectiveness of public service delivery has improved due to streamlined processes.

Citizen Satisfaction

Citizen feedback indicates a high level of satisfaction with the quality and timeliness of public services

The organization actively seeks and addresses citizen feedback to enhance service delivery.

Accessibility

Public services are easily accessible to all segments of the population, regardless of background or ability

The public service actively works to ensure that

(continued on next column)

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(continued)

Statements	Before AI					After AI				
	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	SA	A	N	DA	SDA
services are inclusive and accessible to diverse communities										
The accessibility of public services has improved with the integration of technology and innovation										
Process										
Automation										
Automation of routine tasks through technology has improved the efficiency of public service operations										
The integration of automation technologies has positively impacted the overall speed and accuracy of public service processes										
Data-Driven Decision Making										
Data analytics play a significant role in shaping informed decision-making within the public service										
The use of data-driven insights enhances the efficiency of decision-making processes in public services.										
Public service administrators actively utilize data analytics to optimize service delivery strategies										
Timeliness of Service Delivery										
Public services are consistently delivered within stipulated timeframes.										
The organization places a high priority on ensuring timely delivery of public services.										

(continued on next column)

(continued)

Statements	Before AI					After AI				
	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	SA	A	N	DA	SDA
The public service ensures that time-sensitive services are prioritized and delivered promptly										
Transparency and Accountability										
Processes within the organization are transparent, fostering accountability in public service delivery.										
The organization actively promotes transparency and accountability in its public service operations.										
Transparency in public service operations has increased with the use of technology and innovation										
Adaptability to Changing Needs										
The public service demonstrates flexibility in adapting to changing community needs										
Public services actively seek to understand and respond to emerging challenges in the community.										
I believe that the public service is well-prepared to address new and evolving needs in the community										
Feedback Mechanisms										
Effective feedback mechanisms are in place to gather insights from citizens regarding public services.										
The organization actively uses citizen feedback to drive improvements										

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(continued)

Statements	Before AI					After AI				
	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	SA	A	N	DA	SDA
in public service delivery										
Employee Satisfaction and Productivity										
Employees involved in public service delivery are satisfied with their work and responsibilities										
Employee satisfaction positively contributes to the overall productivity of public service operations										
The public service invests in initiatives to enhance employee satisfaction and well-being										
Environmental Impact										
The organization considers and minimizes the environmental impact of its public service delivery operations.										
Sustainable practices are incorporated into public service delivery to reduce environmental footprint										
Emergency Response Time										
Emergency response services provided by the public service are prompt and effective										
I feel confident in the public service's ability to handle emergency situations efficiently										
The public service has mechanisms in place to continually improve emergency response times										
Compliance with Standards and Regulations										

(continued on next column)

(continued)

Statements	Before AI					After AI				
	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	SA	A	N	DA	SDA
Public services consistently adhere to relevant standards and regulations governing their operations.										
I believe that the public service operates in compliance with legal and regulatory requirements.										
Compliance with standards and regulations is actively monitored and maintained by the public service										
Public Trust and Perception										
I have confidence in the public service's ability to deliver efficient and effective services										
Public services actively work to build and maintain trust with the community.										
The public service's reputation for efficiency positively influences public perception										

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